

Gemini OCS Upgrades: A Blueprint for NOIRLab Operations Software in the 2020s

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Gemini's Observatory Control System (OCS) is the set of high-level software tools for proposal submission through observation execution, for example, the current Phase I Tool (PIT) and the Observing Tool (OT). While these tools have been improving since the start of science operations in 2000, limitations in their design and technology make them difficult to maintain and to update with the capabilities required for the next decades.

Therefore, Gemini/NOIRLab has embarked on an ambitious software development program to replace the entire suite of desktop applications with modern, redesigned, web-based tools. This program is composed of a set of related projects that replace different components of the system using common underlying libraries and interfaces. The goals of the program are to:

- Improve usability—e.g., make proposal and observation preparation much easier;
- Improve efficiency—e.g., improve flexibility and reduce staff workload;
- Support Time Domain Astronomy (TDA)—e.g., provide the software framework for Gemini's new adaptive scheduling tool and application program interfaces (APIs);
- Support new instruments and

Obs. ID	State	Instrum...	Target	Obs. Name
GS-2012B-SV-901-149	Idle	GMOS-S	TNO12345 url	TNO12345 url
GS-2012B-SV-901-205	Idle	GMOS-S	None	Daytime arc

Step	Execution Progress	Offset	Exposure	Disperser	Filter	FPU	Type
1	Pending	0.00* 0.00*	300 [s]	B600 @ 550 nm	Unknown	Longslit 1.00 ar...	OBJECT
2	Pending	0.00* 0.00*	3 [s]	B600 @ 550 nm	Unknown	Longslit 1.00 ar...	FLAT
3	Pending	0.00* 0.00*	20 [s]	B600 @ 550 nm	Unknown	Longslit 1.00 ar...	ARC
4	Pending	0.00* 10.00*	300 [s]	B600 @ 550 nm	Unknown	Longslit 1.00 ar...	OBJECT
5	Pending	0.00* 10.00*	3 [s]	B600 @ 550 nm	Unknown	Longslit 1.00 ar...	FLAT
6	Pending	0.00* 10.00*	20 [s]	B600 @ 550 nm	Unknown	Longslit 1.00 ar...	ARC

Figure 1. Web seqexec client view. (Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA)

systems—e.g., SCORPIO and GNAO;

- Avoid obsolescence—e.g., make the code maintainable and scalable;
- Provide a framework for future telescope operations—e.g., the US ELT Program.

Tremendous progress has been made since this effort was first described in the [October 2017 issue of GeminiFocus](#). This article summarizes recent advances, provides the current timelines, and describes how the community can contribute.

Web-based Sequence Executor

The sequence executor, or seqexec, is the tool that carries out the observation sequences defined in the OT. It communicates with the telescope and instrument hardware in order to manage guiding, do telescope offsets, configure instruments, and take the data. The original version was written in Tcl/Tk as a temporary application. Functional but limited, it remained in use but grew rather ungainly over the years. It is now very hard to find developers who are familiar with Tcl/Tk.

This project has allowed us to solve many technical issues and gain experience with the libraries that will be used for the remaining development.

The Tcl/Tk seqexec has now been replaced with the first product of the OCS Upgrades Program. The new **web seqexec** started being used in regular nightly operations in August, 2020. It is designed with a client-server architecture that is more suited to base-facility operations. The server is written in Scala, a commonly used, modern functional programming language that is the standard of the new system. It runs at the summit and coordinates the use of the hardware. This improves instrument safety since it remains in control of the systems even if communication with the client is lost. It also improves efficiency by allowing simultaneous calibrations with multiple instruments. Multiple users can connect to the server using standard web browsers, allowing easy control and monitoring of activities. A screenshot of a client is shown in Figure 1. This project has allowed us to solve many technical issues and gain experience with the libraries that will be used for the remaining development.

Gemini Program Platform

The Gemini Program Platform (GPP) is the largest of the OCS Upgrades projects and forms the core since it will replace the PIT, OT, and the observing databases. The main concepts were developed from user input over the years, an OCS Upgrades working group that included Gemini and National Gemini Office (NGO) staff

and community representatives, and internal staff discussions. The top-level concepts and changes are as follows:

- It will use scientific or physical descriptions whenever possible (for example wavelength range, spectral resolving power, signal-to-noise ratio, and on-source physical conditions constraints—e.g., IQ in arcsec, extinction in magnitudes—rather than percentile bins);
- Valid, complete observations will be created automatically with the option for user customization;
- Observations with Gemini North and South will be supported in the same science program;
- Interfaces will be available as web applications; no more downloading and installing large desktop applications every semester;
- It will be built around and use the Integration Time Calculators (ITCs) for determining exposure times and signal-to-noise ratios;
- Calibration steps will be generated automatically and the configurations will be kept in sync with the associated science observations;
- Logical observation grouping (e.g., AND/OR) and relative timing constraints between observations will be implemented for organizational flexibility and supporting complex cadences.

The core of the system will be a Postgres database located on a cloud

service. A relational database of this sort has important performance and scalability advantages over the current system. All of the other services and applications will connect to the central database and provide task-specific views of the database. There will also be a set of APIs for enhanced programmatic access.

The community will mainly interact with an application that we call Explore. This is the functional replacement for both the PIT and OT. It is built around the ITCs and also has a “Phase 0” capability for finding and choosing the instruments and modes that meet the requirements on capability, wavelength range, spatial and spectral resolution, etc. A mockup of a possible Explore interface is shown in Figure 2.

GPP passed its Inception (Design) Review in early July 2020 and is now under construction. The documentation is available from the [Operations Development](#) web page. The current project plan has early science use starting in 2022 and operational deployment in 2023.

Adaptive Queue Scheduler

Currently, Gemini queue plans are created manually by the queue coordinators at each site. While of high quality, they can take several hours a day to produce and then can be

Figure 2. A mockup of a possible GPP Explore interface showing target information, constraints, ITC results, and matching configurations (Phase 0). (Credit: NOIRLab/ NSF/AURA)

difficult to modify when changes occur at night. Therefore, we have begun a project to develop an automatic scheduling capability. This will run in real time and create new plans as conditions change and new observations are triggered, for example from alerts originating from the Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST). Both telescopes, North and South, will be scheduled together, thereby increasing the chances of finishing high-priority programs, simplifying some target-of-opportunity programs, and enabling

better coordination between the sites. Intermediate and long-term schedulers that can make recommendations about instrument component swaps and the best times for classical runs are also being investigated. We are currently running a trade study of scheduling algorithms and working towards a design review by mid 2021. This capability should save significant staff effort and make operations more flexible. We expect that the scheduler will be deployed along with GPP in 2023.

This work is being funded in part by the GEMMA supplemental funding award that will also deliver real-time GMOS long-slit data reduction using the DRAGONS pipeline.

Engage

Engage will replace the legacy Tcl/Tk Telescope Control Console (TCC) that is the telescope operator’s main interface for slewing the telescope, configuring the subsystems, and starting the guiding. Engage will use a similar client-server architecture and infrastructure as the web seqexec. The project started in early 2020 and we are currently reviewing the operations concept and working on user interface designs.

Testing and the Future

Community involvement is important for the success of this effort. Suggestions can be submitted using the form provided on the Operations Development page. In 2021 we will be recruiting testers for the early versions of GPP. Stay tuned to the Operations Development web page, the Science Software blog, and future electronic newsletters.

After a couple of years of planning, the OCS Upgrades Program is now producing new tools and actively developing the system that will underpin Gemini operations for the next two decades. The resulting system will be easier to use and easier to maintain. It is also being considered as the core of operations management systems for future facilities that NOIRLab may be involved in, such as the US ELT program. GPP in particular could be readily integrated into a future NOIRLab observing program management and operations system.